

Postnatal Diagnosis of Agnathia-Otocephaly Complex in a Preterm Neonate: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT:

Agnathia-otocephaly complex (AOC) is an extremely rare and typically lethal craniofacial malformation characterized by mandibular hypoplasia or agnathia, ear malposition or fusion, and oropharyngeal anomalies. We report the case of a preterm female neonate delivered via elective caesarean section at 33 weeks gestation, with clinical features consistent with AOC. Despite resuscitative efforts, the neonate succumbed shortly after birth. A de novo mutation in the OTX2 gene is suspected based on the clinical phenotype and positive family history. However, due to sociocultural beliefs and resource limitations, genetic testing was not feasible. This case underscores the importance of prenatal surveillance, recognition of subtle ultrasound findings, multidisciplinary delivery planning, and genetic counselling for families at risk of recurrence.

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INTRODUCTION:

Agnathia-otocephaly complex (AOC) represents a rare and severe spectrum of craniofacial malformations that result from early disruption of the first pharyngeal arch development. These malformations typically manifest as agnathia (absence of mandible), synotia (ventromedial fusion of the ears), and microstomia or aglossia [1,5]. The OTX2 (Orthodenticle Homeobox 2) gene, located on chromosome 14q22.3, plays a critical role in head and brain development, particularly in anterior neural plate formation [2,3].

The condition has an estimated incidence of fewer than 1 in 70,000 live births [4]. Most affected infants are stillborn or die shortly after delivery due to severe airway compromise and associated brain anomalies such as holoprosencephaly [5,9]. *Sporadic occurrences predominate, but autosomal dominant transmission and germline mosaicism have been implicated in recurrent familial cases [3,7,9].* We report a case of AOC identified at birth, highlighting the absence of adequate prenatal testing and its implication for early detection.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 33-week gestational age female neonate was delivered via elective caesarean section to a 34-year-old G6P4+1A3 mother. The procedure was indicated due to suspected fetal anomalies, Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes (PPROM) at 33 weeks, and a history of four previous lower segment caesarean sections.

Birth weight was 1.6 kg; crown-heel length and occipitofrontal circumference were within normal limits. Apgar scores were 2 at 1 minute, and 0 at both 5 and 10 minutes.

Prenatal History: A 34-year-old female, G6P4+1A3 presented to our facility to enrol for

antenatal care about 15 weeks after her last menstrual period. An initial ultrasound scan at that time revealed an active and mobile fetus with normal cardiac activity (FHR: 148 bpm) with an Estimated Gestational Age (EGA) of 14 weeks + 6 days. Amniotic fluid volume was adequate; however, a subchorionic bleed was noted. There was no associated vaginal bleeding, and the patient was advised bed rest with a two-week follow-up appointment.

At follow-up, ultrasound findings remained consistent with subchorionic haemorrhage, though fetal parameters were otherwise normal and the mother remained asymptomatic. The second-trimester 2D anomaly scan was unremarkable, and the pregnancy progressed uneventfully until 32 weeks, when the mother presented with respiratory distress secondary to a rapid increase in abdominal girth. On examination, the symphysis–fundal height measured 52 cm.

2D ultrasonography demonstrated severe polyhydramnios with an Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI) of 49.1 cm. Fetal biometry corresponded to gestational age with a biparietal diameter (BPD) of 7.9 cm, a head circumference (HC) of 29.2 cm, an abdominal circumference (AC) of 28.0 cm, and a femur length (FL) of 6.1 cm. Umbilical artery Doppler showed optimal placental perfusion with Systolic/Diastolic (S/D) ratio: 3.09 cm/sec, and Resistivity Index (RI): 0.68. Fetal morphology assessment revealed the following features:

- **Head:** normal cerebrum, cerebellum, and cavum septi pellucidi
- **Face:** apparent normal facial profile, both orbits present
- **Neck:** no solid or cystic masses
- **Thorax:** normal lungs, hemidiaphragm; normal four-chamber heart and size, good cardiac pulsations

- **Abdomen:** absent stomach bubble with minimal gastric fluid, raising concern for impaired fetal swallowing
- **Other systems:** kidneys, bladder, skeleton, and genitalia appeared normal

The placenta was posterior with normal cord insertion. The biophysical profile score was 6/10, reduced due to absent fetal breathing movements and excessive liquor volume. Overall, the placenta appeared normal, umbilical artery Doppler indices were within the expected range, and no additional structural anomalies were definitively identified aside from the absent stomach bubble and minimal gastric fluid.

Delivery and Postnatal Findings: At delivery, the neonate was flaccid with occasional gasping. Resuscitation was attempted; however, this was hindered by the lack of a definitive airway. The neonate was pronounced dead, shortly after delivery.

Clinical Examination:

Craniofacial anomalies (fig 1)

- Microphthalmia with down-slanting palpebral fissures.
- The nasal bridge was poorly formed with absence of external nose and nasal cavity (arrhinia).
- A cone shaped bulge was observed in the perioral region, with hypoplastic lips and absence of a definitive oral opening. Located superolaterally, on the left side of the bulge was a small orifice, though it is unclear if it opened into an oral cavity.
- There was complete agenesis of the mandible (agnathia).
- The external ears were located anteriorly on the neck with ventromedial fusion (synotia).

Other systems (fig 1)

Trunk, limbs, external genitalia, and umbilical cord were grossly normal.

No visible limb or spinal deformities were observed.

Figure 1a.

Figure 1b.

No autopsy or postmortem imaging was performed due to sociocultural beliefs, and genetic testing was also declined. The mother, however, reported that her first pregnancy had ended in a stillbirth at term. The baby was a male neonate with similar facial abnormalities, suggesting a possible pattern of recurrence. This history had not been disclosed in earlier antenatal period, due to fear of stigma and no follow-up investigations was carried out after that delivery either.

Her follow up visits were uneventful. She was counselled for contraception but declined.

DISCUSSION:

This case is consistent with the Agnathia-Otocephaly Complex. The presence of agnathia, midline craniofacial anomalies, synotia, alongside functional airway compromise, supports the diagnosis [1,4,5].

Pathogenesis and Genetics:

The pathogenesis of AOC lies in the abnormal migration and proliferation of neural crest cells, leading to disrupted development of the first and second pharyngeal arches. OTX2 mutations have been implicated in both isolated AOC and in more complex syndromes involving eye anomalies (anophthalmia/microphthalmia), pituitary dysfunction, and brain malformations like holoprosencephaly [2,3,7,9].

While many cases are de novo, mosaicism or incomplete penetrance may explain familial recurrence. Given the possible recurrence in this case and lack of parental phenotypic abnormality, a germline mosaicism or autosomal dominant OTX2-related mutation is suspected [3,7].

Prenatal Diagnosis and Challenges:

Polyhydramnios, often due to impaired fetal swallowing, is a frequent but nonspecific finding in AOC [4]. In this case, polyhydramnios and absent stomach fluid were the first red flags. The failure to

visualize facial anomalies underscores the limitations of 2D ultrasound, particularly with suboptimal fetal positioning or advanced gestational age. MRI and 3D ultrasound have higher sensitivity in craniofacial anomaly detection [6,10].

Management and Prognosis:

Most neonates with AOC die in utero or shortly after birth due to airway obstruction [5,8]. Some centres advocate for ex utero intrapartum treatment (EXIT) to secure the airway before full delivery in selected prenatally diagnosed cases, though this is rarely feasible in low-resource settings [10,11].

Ethical and Counselling Considerations:

The psychosocial and ethical burden on families is profound. Genetic counselling is critical, especially where recurrence is suspected. Options such as preimplantation genetic testing (PGT), targeted fetal DNA testing, and early fetal anomaly scans should be offered in subsequent pregnancies [9,11,12]. However, availability and affordability of these services remain a big problem in third world countries like Nigeria.

CONCLUSION:

Agnathia-otocephaly complex remains a lethal congenital malformation with devastating perinatal outcomes. This case highlights the diagnostic limitations of prenatal ultrasonography and the importance of detailed family history in guiding suspicion. Integration of advanced imaging modalities and availability of genetic analysis are vital for accurate diagnosis, family counselling, and recurrence risk stratification. Multidisciplinary collaboration is essential for management and emotional support of affected families. However, these interventions may pose a challenge in low resource settings, including that of the index study.

Declarations:

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate-

Ethical approval for the publication of this case report was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of Meridian Hospitals Ltd, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's parent for the publication.

Consent for Publication:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's parent for publication of this case report and any accompanying images

Data Availability:

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article. Additional details or anonymized information can be made available by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing Interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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